

Table S6

Expression	Intersections	Degree	Observed Overlap	Expected Overlap	FE	P.value	pAdj
Upregulated	<i>Monodelphis domestica</i> & <i>Niveoscincus ocellatus</i> & <i>Pseudemoia entrecasteauxii</i> & <i>Rattus norvegicus</i> & <i>Rhizoprionodon taylori</i>	5	1	0.127972736	7.8141644	0.12016643	0.480665721
Upregulated	<i>Bassiana duperreyi</i> & <i>Lampropholis guichenoti</i>	2	1	2.750240709	0.363604537	0.942803255	1
Upregulated	<i>Bassiana duperreyi</i> & <i>Niveoscincus coventryi</i> & <i>Lampropholis guichenoti</i> & <i>Monodelphis domestica</i> & <i>Niveoscincus ocellatus</i> & <i>Pseudemoia entrecasteauxii</i> & <i>Rattus norvegicus</i> & <i>Rhizoprionodon taylori</i>	8	0	1.45E-05	0	1	1
Upregulated	<i>Niveoscincus coventryi</i> & <i>Monodelphis domestica</i> & <i>Niveoscincus ocellatus</i> & <i>Pseudemoia entrecasteauxii</i> & <i>Rattus norvegicus</i> & <i>Rhizoprionodon taylori</i>	6	0	0.018034091	0	1	1
Downregulated	<i>Bassiana duperreyi</i> & <i>Lampropholis guichenoti</i>	2	9	10.85172347	0.829361347	0.766316358	1
Downregulated	<i>Bassiana duperreyi</i> & <i>Niveoscincus coventryi</i> & <i>Lampropholis guichenoti</i> & <i>Monodelphis domestica</i> & <i>Niveoscincus ocellatus</i> & <i>Pseudemoia entrecasteauxii</i> & <i>Rattus norvegicus</i> & <i>Rhizoprionodon taylori</i>	8	0	1.61E-06	0	1	1
Downregulated	<i>Niveoscincus coventryi</i> & <i>Monodelphis domestica</i> & <i>Niveoscincus ocellatus</i> & <i>Pseudemoia entrecasteauxii</i> & <i>Rattus norvegicus</i> & <i>Rhizoprionodon taylori</i>	6	0	0.000508249	0	1	1
Downregulated	<i>Monodelphis domestica</i> & <i>Niveoscincus ocellatus</i> & <i>Pseudemoia entrecasteauxii</i> & <i>Rattus norvegicus</i> & <i>Rhizoprionodon taylori</i>	5	0	0.010578161	0	1	1